

Exploration and Research of Music Image in Anhui Han Stone Sculpture

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ABSTRACT

When tracing the history of ancient music culture, the Han Dynasty stone statue in Anhui has become a window to spy on the past. These stone carvings have a history of more than a thousand years, carrying the life scenes, aesthetic concepts and social culture of people in the Han Dynasty. Music, as the common language of human society, is passed down through these images and becomes a link between the present and the past. Anhui Han stone sculpture is one of the precious heritages of ancient Chinese culture and art, which contains rich musical images. The purpose of this paper is to explore the music images in Anhui Han stone sculptures, analyze their artistic style, musical elements and cultural connotation, and reveal the relationship between ancient music and social life. Through the detailed study of a number of Han Dynasty stone sculptures in Anhui, we find that music played an important role in the life of ancient people, which profoundly reflects the music culture of the society at that time. Through the analysis of music images, we can further understand the Musical Instruments, playing forms and social functions of ancient music, which provides a powerful perspective for us to understand ancient society.

Keywords: Anhui, Han Dynasty Stone Relief, Music Image, Image Analysis.

INTRODUCTION

As the inheritor of a long history and rich culture, China carries a rich and diverse artistic heritage. In this cultural treasure house, as a special art form, Anhui Han stone sculpture has irreplaceable historical value and artistic significance. With their exquisite carving techniques and vivid scenes, these stone reliefs show us fragments of ancient social life, including rich music images (Smith, 2007). These images record different scenes of ancient people's gathering, sacrifice, entertainment and so on accompanied by music, which restores a real and vivid picture of ancient music culture for us (Y. Liu, 2012).

However, due to the baptism of time and other natural factors, these ancient stone statues have suffered varying degrees of loss in preservation (Wu, 2005). In order to better understand and protect these cultural heritages, it is necessary to conduct systematic and in-depth research on them. Especially in modern society, the progress of science and technology gives us more means to interpret these ancient works and dig out the valuable information in them (Anhui Museum, 2010). Therefore, the study of the music images in the Han Dynasty stone sculptures in Anhui helps to pass on these precious historical heritages and let them continue to shine in the long river of time (W. Zhang, 2018).

As an important part of human society, music reflects many factors such as society, culture and emotion. Ancient music is a field with rich cultural connotations, which is closely related to religion, ritual, social interaction and emotion. Through the study of the music images in the Han Dynasty stone sculptures in Anhui, we can restore the multidimensional features of ancient music from the perspective of art and deeply understand how the ancient people understood, expressed and practised music. First, studying these musical images can help us reconstruct the forms and instruments of ancient music (M. Liu, 2009). In these portraits, the ancient people used clever strokes to depict a variety of different instruments, showing the ancient musicians' playing posture

and playing scenes. Through the interpretation of these instruments (X. L. Wu, 2015), we can understand how ancient musicians used these instruments to create beautiful musical sounds and the role of music in ancient social life. Secondly, these stone sculptures also reflect the role of ancient music in social interaction and entertainment. In ancient societies, music was often an integral part of people's gatherings and celebrations. By studying the banquet, dance, and entertainment scenes depicted in these images, we can gain insight into how ancient people used music to express emotions, strengthen social bonds, and how music into their daily lives (Y. Chen, 2013). In addition, they may contain religious and mythological elements. In ancient societies, music played an important role in religious rituals and was used to communicate with gods or pray. By analyzing the religious scenes in these images, we can learn about the mysterious and sublime role of ancient music in religious rituals, and how music plays a role in mythological stories. Finally, the study of music images in Anhui Han Dynasty stone reliefs can also help us understand the changes and inheritance of ancient music culture. Music has evolved over time and has been influenced by different cultures, but it has always maintained its character as a common language across time and space (Q. Wang, 2017). By studying the forms of music in different historical stages in these images, we can reveal the development of ancient musical culture and how it influenced the musical traditions of later generations. To sum up, it is of great historical, cultural and artistic significance to study the music images in Anhui Han stone sculptures (Li, 2011). Through the in-depth analysis of these images, we can restore the multidimensional features of ancient music and understand the ancient people's aesthetic taste, social life and spiritual world (Tang, 2008).

The research goal of this paper is to reveal the expression form, artistic characteristics and cultural connotation of ancient music through the in-depth analysis of the music images in the Han Dynasty stone sculptures in Anhui. Specifically, we will carry out the research from the following aspects: First, we will classify and sort the music images of Han Dynasty stone reliefs in Anhui, and explore the commonalities and characteristics of different types of images. Through the analysis of these images, we can understand how ancient music was presented in different scenes. Secondly, we will give an in-depth analysis of the artistic style of these musical images.

From painting techniques and the use of colour to composition features, we will explore how artists bring music scenes to life through pen and ink. Then, we will explore the musical elements contained in these images. Musical Instruments and performance forms are an important part of ancient music. Through the interpretation of musical instrument types and performance forms in the images, we can restore the diversity of ancient music and performance scenes. In addition, we will explore the cultural connotations reflected in these musical images. As a part of culture, music often contains profound social meaning and emotional expression. By analyzing the scenes of social life in the images and the possible elements of myth and legend, we can gain insight into the place and role of music in ancient culture. Finally, we will start from these music images to explore the relationship between ancient music and social life, as well as the change and inheritance of ancient music culture. Through these analyses, we hope to restore a more real and rich picture of ancient music.

RESEARCH METHODS

When exploring the musical and cultural significance of the music images in the Han Dynasty stone sculptures in Anhui Province, the choice of research methods becomes very important. This chapter will introduce in detail the research methods used, including image analysis, historical textual research, and comparative analysis of art history. At the same time, we must also recognize the limitations and challenges faced by these methods in the research process (M. Zhang, 2019).

Research Methods

Image Analysis

Image analysis is an important method for the in-depth study of music images of Han Dynasty stone reliefs. By carefully observing the visual elements of the image, such as the composition, use of colour, and expression of lines, we can interpret the emotion and information conveyed by the image. When analyzing the form of Musical Instruments, we can explore the appearance and structure of Musical Instruments in the Han Dynasty (Huang, 2014), and speculate the timbre and playing mode of Musical Instruments. From the movements of the performers, we can infer the nature of the music, so as to understand the rhythm and rhythm characteristics of Han Dynasty music.

Historical Document Research

Historical documents provide precious records of Han Dynasty music and provide valuable references for the interpretation of music images (Xu, 2016). By combining the records with historical documents, we can further

verify the musical elements in the images and increase the credibility of the research. There may be references to the names of Musical Instruments, the occasions in which music was played, and the place of music in society (Guo, 2010). It is helpful for us to better understand the cultural background and meaning of the music scene presented by the images to confirm each other with the literature.

Comparative Analysis of Art History

By comparing with music-related images of other times and regions, we can better grasp the uniqueness of music images of the Han Dynasty. The comparative analysis of art history helps us to deeply explore the artistic characteristics and cultural value of Han Dynasty music images from the aspects of image style, expression technique and subject matter. Comparative analysis can also reveal musical inheritance and change in different time periods, further expanding our understanding of musical images.

Research Limitations and Challenges

Image Ambiguity

Although the music images in Anhui Han stone sculptures are vivid, they are often ambiguous. Different viewers may have different interpretations of the same image because of their different cultural backgrounds and perspectives. Therefore, when interpreting images, we must be careful and consider many possibilities, so as not to fall into the trap of being overly subjective (M. Chen, 2018).

Insufficient and Incomplete literature

The historical literature on Han Dynasty music culture is relatively limited, which restricts our in-depth understanding of Han Dynasty music to a certain extent. Some musical details and the cultural connotations behind them may not be adequately documented in the literature (X. Wang, 2013), which can also affect our accurate interpretation of the image. When using historical documents, we need to carefully weigh the reliability of different sources and try to extrapolate from multiple perspectives.

Interdisciplinary Challenge

The study of the music images in Anhui Han Dynasty stone sculptures requires the involvement of art history, musicology, history and other disciplines. There may be differences in terminology and methods between different disciplines (F. Liu, 2017), requiring researchers to have an interdisciplinary knowledge background and research skills in order to better interpret images and blend knowledge from different fields.

Image Loss and Defects

As an ancient cultural relic, the Han Dynasty stone statues in Anhui have been eroded by wind and rain for thousands of years, and some of the images may have wear and tear and defects. These losses may affect our observation and analysis of image details. In the image analysis, we must consider these factors, so as not to mislead the interpretation of the image.

Complexity of Social Background

The social background of the Han Dynasty is very complicated, and there are differences between different historical periods and regions. Therefore, when we interpret the music images in Anhui Han stone sculptures, we need to put them in a specific historical and cultural background. This helps us better understand the message of images and the place and role of music in society at the time.

Summary

By using the methods of image analysis, historical literature research and art history comparative analysis, we can understand the music cultural significance contained in the music images of Han Dynasty stone sculptures in Anhui more comprehensively. However, these methods also face certain limitations and challenges, and we need to be cautious and creative in the research process to overcome these difficulties.

For image analysis, we should pay attention to the ambiguity of the image, try to interpret the image with an objective vision, and use advanced technologies and tools, such as digital image processing and three-dimensional reconstruction, to study the details of the image more deeply.

In terms of historical literature research, although there may be deficiencies and incompleteness in the literature, we can enhance our understanding of Han Dynasty music by extensively collecting documents from different sources, comparing documents from multiple periods, and combining archaeological findings.

For the challenge of interdisciplinarity, researchers need to expand their own knowledge field and seek interdisciplinary cooperation in order to study the multiple dimensions of music images more comprehensively.

In terms of loss and defects, the use of advanced cultural relic protection technology can help to restore and

protect Han stone sculptures to ensure their long-term preservation and the feasibility of research.

Most importantly, we should place the music images in the social context of the Han Dynasty and have a deep understanding of the culture, religion, politics and social system at that time, so as to better understand the cultural value and historical significance of these images.

In conclusion, the study of music images in Anhui Han Dynasty stone sculptures is a complex and exciting task, which requires a multi-faceted approach and continuous efforts. By overcoming these methodological challenges, we can better explore and pass on the precious heritage of Han Dynasty music.

MUSIC IMAGES OF HAN DYNASTY STONE RELIEF IN ANHUI

When we deeply explore the music images in the Han Dynasty stone sculptures in Anhui, we not only reveal the multiple levels of ancient music culture but also involve the cross-research of many disciplines. This chapter will focus on the analysis and interpretation of the music images in the Han Dynasty stone sculptures in Anhui Province, and explore their role in ancient music culture, symbolic significance and influence on the music of later generations by examining the portraits of different periods and themes (L. Zhang, 2012).

Portrait Classification and Characteristic Analysis

In the study of the music images in Anhui Han stone sculptures, we need to classify and analyze the characteristics of the portraits first. According to the different contents and scenes, these portraits can be roughly divided into banquet scenes, religious ceremony scenes, dance entertainment scenes, etc. Each type of portrait shows the use and representation of ancient music in different scenes (Figure 1).

Figure 1. Portrait Classification

Banquet Scene

In the portraits of banquet scenes, you can often see musicians playing their instruments and people enjoying the music around them. These portraits vividly reproduce the scene of ancient people gathering and communicating, and music as an important part of social activities has been fully reflected. By analyzing the movements of musicians and the shape of Musical Instruments in the picture, we can infer the performance of ancient musicians, music types and other information. For example, some of the musicians in the portraits may be playing the guqin, the flute, or the drum, instruments that reflect the variety of music at the time.

Religious Ceremony Scenarios

In the images of religious ceremony scenes, music is often used to communicate with the gods and enhance the atmosphere of sacrifice. These images show the role of musicians in religious rituals and reveal the importance of music in religious life. By studying the types of Musical Instruments in the picture and the musicians' costumes, we can understand the specific role and form of ancient music in religious ceremonies (Wei, 2015). Religious ceremonies often require solemn and solemn music to create a sacred atmosphere, which puts forward certain requirements for musicians' skills and music choices.

Dance Entertainment Scene

In the portrait of the dance entertainment scene, music is often an important factor in promoting the rhythm and emotional expression of the dance. These portraits depict scenes of people dancing happily, showing the close connection between music and dance in ancient entertainment. By analyzing the movement of musicians and the posture of dancers, we can explore how music and dance interact to create a pleasant audio-visual experience. Ancient music is not only a kind of auditory enjoyment but also interwoven with other art forms to create a multi-sensory artistic experience.

The Symbolic Meaning of Music in the Portrait

The music images in the Han Dynasty stone relief in Anhui are not only the reproduction of ancient music life but also contain rich symbolic significance. Music in these portraits is not only a form of artistic expression, but also a cultural, social and emotional symbol (Figure 2).

Figure 2. The Symbolic Meaning of Music in a Portrait

Social Connection and Emotional Expression

In the portraits in banquet scenes and dance entertainment scenes, music often represents the social connection and emotional expression between people. People sit together and enjoy music together, demonstrating the importance of social interaction. The dancers dancing with the accompaniment of music is also an expression of emotions, and joy and other emotions are conveyed through dance. The expression of these emotions not only enriches the connotation of the portrait but also reveals the role of music in social and emotional communication.

Religious Worship and Mystical Power

In depictions of religious ritual scenes, music is often used to worship deities and convey a mystical power. Through the timbre and rhythm of music, people try to communicate with the supernatural world and express their respect and prayer for the gods. Music in these scenes acts as a bridge between man and God, with a symbolic meaning that transcends the physical world. This symbolic meaning played an important role in ancient religious culture and also had a profound impact on later religious music.

Cultural Inheritance and Identity

Music images in Anhui Han Dynasty stone sculptures also reflect the important role of music in cultural inheritance and identity. Through these portraits, we can glimpse the importance of music in ancient society and the status of music in society. As a medium of cultural inheritance, music is used to pass on history, values and traditions. The music scene depicted in the portrait is not only a personal pleasure, but also a cultural heritage passed down from generation to generation. The inheritance of musicians' skills and the evolution of Musical Instruments have all left valuable historical information in the portrait.

In addition, musical images also reflect the identities of different social groups. People from different walks of life and occupations participate in musical activities in the portrait, demonstrating their roles and status in society (Figure 3). For example, the aristocracy might enjoy elegant music in banquet scenes, while the common people might enjoy popular music and dance in temple fairs or entertainment venues. These different music scenes and characters reflect the stratification and differences in society at the time and also demonstrate the influence of music among different groups.

Figure 3. Identity Mapping

By analyzing these music images, we can better understand the multiple aspects of ancient music culture in society, not only artistic expression but also the carrier of cultural inheritance, social interaction and identity. The influence of this music culture has continued in the later generations and has had a profound impact on the development and evolution of Chinese traditional music.

Social Functions of Music Images

The image of music in Anhui Han Dynasty stone relief is not only an artistic expression but also has an important social function. These images depict people's musical activities on various occasions, such as banquets, temple fairs, entertainment, etc., which reflects the social function of music in society. Music is not only the enjoyment of art but also a way for people to communicate and interact. On banquet occasions, music can enhance the atmosphere and make people happier; In temple fairs, music is part of a religious ritual and helps to guide the worshippers into a religious atmosphere. In entertainment venues, music becomes a means of social entertainment and helps people connect.

The social function of these musical images also reflects the vitality and diversity of society at the time. People use music to celebrate festivals, entertain guests, participate in religious ceremonies, etc., and these activities need music as a background or impetus. Music is not only the exclusive domain of musicians and performers but also a cultural activity that the general public participates in. These musical images show people's joy, communication and exchange on various occasions, reflecting the social life of ancient society.

ARTISTIC STYLE ANALYSIS OF MUSIC IMAGES

Painting Techniques and Expression Techniques

In the music images in Anhui Han stone sculptures, artists skillfully used various painting techniques and expression techniques to convey the scene and emotion of the music performance. The clever use of these techniques and techniques gives the music image a vivid appeal.

First of all, we can observe that in the musical image, the performance of the figure is quite subtle. The artists use exquisite lines to describe the player's posture, expression and the shape of the instrument. For example, a guqin player in a painting might be depicted with an attentive expression, fingers playing the music with dexterity, and the vibrations of the strings might be represented by delicate lines. This painting technique allows the viewer to feel the dedication and passion of the musicians as if the music is echoing in front of their eyes (Figure 4).

Figure 4. Music Images in Anhui Han Dynasty Stone Relief

Secondly, the use of colour also plays an important role in music images. Different colour combinations can convey different emotions and atmospheres. For example, soft colours are often used to represent quiet musical scenes, while bright colours may be used to emphasize intense musical performances. By contrasting the light and dark changes of colour, artists can enhance the layers of the picture, making the music image more three-dimensional and visually appealing.

In addition, the combination of virtuality and reality is also a significant feature of Anhui Han stone relief music images. In some images, the artist may portray the player as relatively realistic, but the background or part of the instrument is presented in a slightly blurred or simplified way, which makes the focus more prominent. This combination of virtuality and reality makes the viewer's eyes naturally focus on the player and the instrument, further strengthening the expressive force of the music image.

Colour Application and Composition Characteristics

In terms of the colour application and composition characteristics of the music images of Han Dynasty stone relief in Anhui, we can see a series of carefully designed techniques to show the resonance between music and vision.

First, the choice of colours often coincides with the musical scenes and emotions depicted. For example, when depicting upbeat, passionate music scenes, artists may use warm colours such as bright red and orange to convey enthusiasm and energy. In the performance of quiet, quiet music scenes, elegant blue, green and other cool colours may be more appropriate, making the picture appear peaceful and quiet.

Secondly, composition is also one of the elements that can not be ignored in music images. Through reasonable composition, artists can organically integrate musical elements and characters to create a harmonious and unified picture effect. For example, the player in the picture may be placed on one side of the picture, leaving a certain space to represent the instrument and musical elements. This composition technique makes the music image more vivid and rhythmic as if the music is moving in the picture.

In addition, diagonals and contrasts are often used to build a sense of motion. For example, an instrument holder's arm may extend diagonally, intersecting with other lines, which can give a sense of movement and vitality (Figure 5). At the same time, by forming a contrast between light and dark, thickness, virtual and real in the picture, the artist can enhance the tension and three-dimensional sense of the picture, making the music image more attractive.

Figure 5. Dynamic Sense of Han Dynasty Stone Relief in Anhui

Through the above analysis, we can see that the artistic style of the music images in Anhui Han stone sculptures is rich and colourful, and the application of techniques and techniques makes these images vividly reproduce the scenes and emotions of ancient music. Through an in-depth understanding of these artistic styles, we can better grasp the expression mode and artistic characteristics of ancient music culture. Next, we will continue to explore the musical elements in musical images, starting from the instruments and performance forms, to further reveal the face of ancient music.

CASE STUDY OF HAN DYNASTY STONE RELIEF IN ANHUI

In this chapter, we will choose two representative Anhui Han stone relief works for in-depth analysis and interpretation, in order to show the music image, artistic style, composition characteristics and cultural connotation.

Case 1: Han Dynasty stone relief in Xiaoxian County, Anhui Province

The Han Dynasty stone statue of Xiaoxian County, Anhui Province is a well-preserved Han Dynasty stone statue, which is famous for its rich content and exquisite artistic techniques. It contains a number of music images, which provide an important reference for us to study Han Dynasty music culture (Figure 6).

Figure 6. Han Dynasty Stone Relief in Xiaoxian County, Anhui Province

First, let's look at the musical instrument image in the stone. On this stone, we can clearly see different kinds of Musical Instruments, such as drums, flutes and so on. These instruments are displayed with fine carvings and meticulous lines, showing the highly developed technique of instrument making and performance in the Han Dynasty.

Secondly, several musicians are depicted in the stone. They wear gorgeous clothes, hold Musical Instruments, and have different shapes and lifelike. Through careful observation of them, we can infer the social status and role of their musicians and also show the shape and image of Han Dynasty musicians.

In addition, various musical performance scenes are also presented in the stone sculptures. For example, there is a banquet scene in the portrait, people sit together on the left, the artists play Musical Instruments, and some dance, the whole scene is full of joy and energy. This suggests that music played an important social and entertainment role in Han society.

Through the analysis of this case, we can see the rich diversity and fine production technology of music images in Han Dynasty stone relief in Xiaoxian County, Anhui province. These images not only provide precious materials of Musical Instruments and musicians but also reveal the grandeur and characteristics of Han Dynasty music culture.

Case 2: Han Dynasty stone relief in HUAIBEI, Anhui Province

The Han Dynasty stone relief in Huaibei, Anhui Province is another important case, showing different musical images and artistic characteristics. The stone is a larger stone tablet with multiple music scenes carved on it, giving us a deeper understanding of the expression of Han Dynasty music culture.

In this stone, we can see groups of musicians playing their instruments. They were dressed in splendid robes and carried Musical Instruments, some playing the flute, others the lute. Their images are vivid and concrete, showing the costumes, gestures and musical instrument-playing skills of Han Dynasty musicians (Figure 7).

Figure 7. Han Dynasty Stone Relief in Huaibei, Anhui Province

In addition to the images of musicians, the stone sculptures also depict scenes of various musical performances. For example, there is a musical scene with a crown and dancers holding instruments to move to the rhythm of the music. This scene vividly shows the splendour of music and dance in the Han Dynasty and also reflects the important role of music in religious and ceremonial activities at that time.

In addition, the stone sculptures also depict the communication scenes between musicians and social celebrities such as officials and noblewomen. These scenes reflect the role of music in connecting different classes and promoting social interaction in Han society. At the same time, these images also show the society's worship and respect for musicians at that time.

Through the analysis of Han Dynasty stone statues in Huaibei, Anhui, we can further understand the diversity and artistic expression of Han Dynasty music images. These images present musicians, instruments and music performance scenes, revealing the richness and diversity of Han Dynasty music culture for us.

To sum up, through the analysis of the above two cases, we can see the richness and uniqueness of the music images in Anhui Han stone sculptures. Through exquisite carving and meticulous depiction, these images show the glorious scene of Han Dynasty musical culture, while also providing important clues for our understanding of ancient musical customs, religious beliefs and social activities.

RECONSTRUCTION OF THE HAN DYNASTY MUSIC SCENE

The Method of Image Analysis for Music Scene Reconstruction

As an important part of ancient works of art, image analysis can provide valuable clues about the music scene of the Han Dynasty. The methods of image analysis include the observation and interpretation of figures, Musical Instruments, gestures, and environment in images. Combining the knowledge of archaeology, musicology and history, these analysis results can be restored to the possible appearance of the music scene of the Han Dynasty.

Roles and Images of Musicians

In Han Dynasty stone sculptures, musicians are one of the key roles in the music scene. By analyzing the musicians' clothing, gestures, facial expressions and other details in the portraits, we can infer their roles during the performance. The images of musicians reveal the professional and social status of music performance in the Han Dynasty. They may have been court musicians, or they may have been practitioners of skills among the common people.

Reproduction of Musical Instruments and Musical Elements

The reconstruction of the Han music scene involves not only the musicians themselves but also the instruments and musical elements used. Through a careful study of the Musical Instruments that appear in Han Dynasty stone sculptures, we can reveal the diversity and expression of Han Dynasty music. The shape, size, and playing style of the different instruments and their position in the portrait can help us to reconstruct the sounds and emotions of ancient music.

In terms of Musical Instruments, Han Dynasty stone sculptures often depict a variety of Musical Instruments, including strings, wind, percussion and so on. For example, string instruments such as the qin, se, and zheng may have played an important role in court musical occasions, while wind instruments such as the flute and xiao may have been used for different types of performances, such as celebrations or religious ceremonies. In addition, the percussion instruments that may appear in the portrait, such as drums and cymbals, may have been used to enhance the sense of rhythm and atmosphere. By studying these instruments, we can infer the style and atmosphere of Han Dynasty music.

In addition, the way the instrument is played and the musical elements are also the key research objects. An instrument's posture, gestures, and ensemble relationships with other instruments can give us clues about how musicians create and express music. Han music probably incorporated a variety of rhythms, melodies, and timbres, and these elements were reflected in the interaction between instruments and players.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Through the in-depth analysis of the music images in Anhui Han stone sculptures, we find some common characteristics and trends. These images not only show scenes of ancient music performances but also convey important elements of the social music culture of the Han Dynasty. In these images, we can see the interaction between musicians, instruments and the audience, reflecting the social nature of ancient music. The finely depicted instruments in the hands of the musicians demonstrate the high level of musical craftsmanship of the Han Dynasty. In addition, some music images may also contain symbolic meaning, which may be related to social status, religious beliefs and other factors.

The common features of these music images indicate the importance of music in Han society and the role of music in social life. However, we also noticed variations between the different images, which may reflect the context of The Times and regional differences. This provides clues for further research on the diversity of Han Dynasty music culture.

CONCLUSION

Through the in-depth study of the music images in the Han Dynasty stone sculptures in Anhui, we can get a glimpse of the Han Dynasty music culture. These images are not only ancient artworks but also an important

window into Han society, culture and music. Through the analysis of images, we can restore the ancient music scene, feel the skills of Han Dynasty musicians, and the influence of music on the life of ancient people.

This study highlights the importance of cultural images that not only reflect the aesthetics and values of a particular period but also carry a wealth of historical information. However, it is also important to note that the interpretation of images may be affected by subjective factors of the researcher, so a multi-angle, multi-disciplinary approach is the key to a deep understanding of ancient culture.

AUTHOR CONTRIBUTIONS

The author's contributions are equally in the manuscript.

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